

**IMPLEMENTATION AND LEGAL BASIS OF THE PROSECUTOR'S
CONTROL OVER LAW ENFORCEMENT IN GENERAL SECONDARY,
SPECIAL SECONDARY AND PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL
INSTITUTIONS**

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Аннотация. Мазкур мақолада умумий ўрта, ўрта махсус ва профессионал таълим муассасаларида қонунчилик ижроси устидан прокурор назоратининг жорий этилиши ва ҳуқуқий асосларининг ўзига хос хусусиятлари ва корреляциявий таҳлил усулидан фойдаланган ҳолда ўрганиб чиқилиб, тизим салоҳиятини оширишга қаратилган таклифлар ишлаб чиқилган.

Калит сўзлар: прокурор назорати, прокуратура органлари, вояга етмаганлар, махсус ҳуқуқий мақоми принципи, превентив чоралар, халқаро стандарт, норматив-ҳуқуқий қоидалар.

Аннотация. В данной статье с использованием метода корреляционного анализа и особенностей прокурорского надзора изучено внедрение прокурорского надзора за исполнением законодательства в учреждениях общего среднего, среднего специального и профессионального образования, а также разработаны предложения, направленные на повышение потенциала данной системы.

Ключевые слова: прокурорский надзор, прокуратура, несовершеннолетние, принцип особого правового статуса, меры пресечения, международный стандарт, нормативные правовые положения.

Abstract. In this article, the introduction of prosecutor's control over the implementation of legislation in general secondary, secondary special and professional educational institutions is studied, using the method of correlational analysis and

specific features of the prosecutor's control, and proposals aimed at increasing the potential of the system are developed.

Keywords: prosecutor's supervision, prosecutor's office, minors, principle of special legal status, preventive measures, international standard, regulatory legal provisions.

In our country, ensuring legality in general secondary, specialized, and professional educational institutions is considered one of the priority goals in accordance with the requirements of the time. Protecting the rights and legal interests of students, pupils, and teachers, as well as enhancing social protection and a prosperous future for those who have not yet reached their potential, is directly related to the effectiveness of legal relations in this field, including the activities of any competent authority, especially the prosecutor's office.

The effective implementation of legal oversight by the prosecutor in general secondary, specialised, and professional educational institutions involves conducting thorough investigations using a **correlational analysis method** to verify the legal foundations. This process includes identifying regulatory gaps in the field and shaping strategies to address them, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of prosecutorial oversight and ensuring the proper and qualitative implementation of monitoring measures, which is of great importance.

It is essential to emphasise that there are several legal documents aimed at regulating the implementation of prosecutorial oversight in this field, and it is crucial to ensure compliance with them. Among these documents, the Constitution is considered the most fundamental one.

From a legal perspective, the Constitution serves as the most crucial and fundamental document, serving as the basis for other laws and regulations in terms of its legal significance. In essence, constitutional norms, including the established rules and principles within it, form the legal basis of the country [1].

In particular, the specification of the norms governing the oversight by the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the prosecutors subordinate to

it over the precise and uniform enforcement of laws within the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan as delineated in the Constitution highlights its paramount importance in ensuring the legal compliance of oversight in the implementation of legal practices in general secondary, specialized, and professional educational institutions.

What exactly is the Constitution? It is **primarily regarded** as the fundamental key that determines the main directions of the state and social development and their structuring. The Constitution is the highest legal document that regulates the life of the state and society. Its norms establish the principles, forms, and methods of state policy, as well as strengthen the mechanism for its implementation, aimed at organizing the life of the state and society.

The main law, with its significance, stands as one of the essential foundations of any democratic society, as it enshrines the legal rights of individuals and communities, the organization of state authority, and the functioning of its institutions.

Therefore, all laws and other regulatory legal documents must be in accordance with the constitution. In this regard, according to the viewpoint of A. Ochilov, "**The Constitution of Uzbekistan is a document possessing significant legal power in protecting the rights of youth**"[2]. In light of these opinions, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is considered the most important document for the implementation of prosecutorial oversight in ensuring legal compliance in general secondary, specialized, and professional educational institutions by the prosecutor's offices.

Especially, the inclusion of the XIV section titled "Family, Children, and Youth"[3] in the Constitution, adopted in the new edition through the public voting process during the referendum of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 30, 2023, underscores the attention paid to the youth in general secondary, specialized, and professional educational institutions on the present day. This section ensures the protection of the personal, political, economic, social, civil, and environmental rights of young people, as well as the creation of conditions for their intellectual, creative, physical, and moral development, and the establishment of terms and conditions for

the realization of their rights to education, health care, housing, employment, and self-realization.

Drawing conclusions from the findings of the research, it is possible to analyze the legal basis of prosecutorial oversight in terms of ensuring legal compliance in general secondary, specialized, and professional educational institutions in two main directions.

In the first aspect, the analysis focuses on the presentation of the normative legal documents related to the protection of the rights of students in general secondary, specialized, and professional educational institutions and highlights the detailed examination of the effective and uniform installation of laws in this field by the relevant prosecutorial authorities.

In the second aspect, the study pays attention to the establishment of the relationships associated with the organization of prosecutorial oversight in the implementation of legal compliance in general secondary, specialized, and professional educational institutions, particularly considering the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prosecutor's Office"[4] and the provisions and directives of the Prosecutor General.

The organization of prosecutorial oversight in the implementation of legal compliance in general secondary, specialized, and professional educational institutions is directly governed by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prosecutor's Office." Primarily, based on Article 3 of this law, the establishment of prosecutorial authorities and the procedure for their activities, as well as their responsibilities, are determined in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this law, and other legal documents. Moreover, this law specifies the main tasks of prosecutorial authorities, the main directions of their activities, the supervision of legal compliance, its subject, and the powers of the prosecutor in the implementation of legal compliance oversight.

It is essential to note that the field of general secondary, specialized, and professional education is quite complex, and thus, additional responsibilities are

assigned to the prosecutorial authorities by the laws and regulatory legal documents related to ensuring the proper functioning of these institutions. Indeed, not only the activities of general secondary, specialized, and professional educational institutions but also all aspects of prosecutorial oversight in the implementation of legal compliance are governed by the Law "On the Prosecutor's Office" and its fundamental directives, accepted on the basis of the decrees of the Prosecutor General.

Similarly, the other legal foundations of prosecutorial oversight in the implementation of legal compliance in general secondary, specialized, and professional educational institutions are also defined by the Civil and Family Codes of the Republic of Uzbekistan, particularly in laws such as "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child," "On Youth Policy," "On Guardianship and Trusteeship," "On Prevention of Neglect and Juvenile Delinquency," and "On the Protection of Children from Information Harmful to Their Health." These normative legal documents play a crucial role in regulating social relations concerning minors.

Specifically, the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child" from January 7, 2008, and "On Prevention of Neglect and Juvenile Delinquency" from September 29, 2010, serve a particular purpose in ensuring the protection of the rights and freedoms of minors, highlighting their vulnerability and the need for protection against negligence, violation of rights, and delinquency.

Moreover, Articles 4 and 5 of the Law "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child" specifically outline a number of critical tasks as the main directions of state policy, including ensuring the rights, freedoms, and legal interests of the child, protecting the child's life and health, preventing the child's exploitation, protecting the child's honor and dignity, ensuring the equality of children's rights and opportunities, and improving the legal basis of the guarantees of children's rights. N. Dusmukhamedova aptly describes the Law "On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child" as being created on the basis of international legal norms, just as the UN Charter serves as the international Constitution for all states. Thus, this law fulfills its own constitutional duty for children[5].

In our view, this law is considered highly significant in ensuring the protection of the rights and legal interests of students in general secondary, specialized, and professional educational institutions, as well as in further developing and strengthening the legal framework in the field. It plays a crucial role in defining the main directions of the activities of state authorities in securing their rights. Indeed, emphasizing the uniform implementation of laws in general secondary, specialized, and professional educational institutions significantly contributes to ensuring the majority of students' rights are safeguarded by the state.

In our opinion, these normative legal documents have established guarantees for children who are not under parental care relative to the general, specialized, and professional education sectors. Therefore, the implementation of oversight based on the principle of safeguarding the rights and legal interests of children, as stipulated in the laws, is necessary.

The protection of the legal rights of children without parental care is based on several international instruments established from the perspective of an individual legal status. One of the most crucial among these international documents is the Convention on the Rights of the Child, adopted by the United Nations. In this convention, children are recognized as individuals with special rights.

In addition to these, the "Convention on the Rights of the Child on the Sale of Children, Child Prostitution and Child Pornography," the International Labour Organization's (ILO) Convention No. 182, the Council of Europe's "Convention on the Protection of Children against Sexual Exploitation and Sexual Abuse," the "African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child," and the "Declaration on the Protection of Children in Asia"[6] are all in place. They specifically highlight the unique vulnerabilities of children without parental care and emphasize the necessity for tailored protection and support as international legal standards.

Indeed, the recognition of these circumstances as international standards directly relates to the additional protection needed for children without parental care compared to others in general, middle, and professional education.

Indeed, Norway, Sweden, and Denmark, like other Scandinavian countries, are renowned for their special attention to the well-being and rights of children, and the prosecutors in these countries have extensive powers to ensure the implementation of legal documents related to the protection of children in general, middle, and professional education. It is possible to observe their special consideration for the unique legal status of children without parental care in dealing with issues related to safety, vulnerability, and other rights violations[7].

In addition, according to A.S. Arutyunyan, "Regarding the legal oversight of the rights of unaccompanied minors, the Prosecutor's Office in the Russian Federation has a particular role, namely, the special position of unaccompanied minors is emphasized."

From the above, it can be concluded that in our country, it is necessary to find the reflection of the above-mentioned principles in the normative documents aimed at ensuring the rights of children. This, in turn, emphasizes that ensuring the rights and legal interests of unaccompanied minors is one of the most important tasks of state policy and that they should be given separate attention by the state. Moreover, it is of great importance to identify the potential in the international arena to protect the rights and legal interests of unaccompanied minors in our country.

It should be emphasized separately that without the effective activity of specialized authorities in the field, the rights and freedoms of unaccompanied minors are not adequately protected, and the prevention of negligence and violations, including crime, among unaccompanied minors is not possible.

According to the well-known legal professor Mary Carrington, "Prosecutors need to ensure the protection of justice from the weakest links of society and that their voices are heard in the legal system" [8]. In the context of the aforementioned opinion, significant changes are also being implemented in this field in our country until the present day.

In this regard, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Neglect and Juvenile Delinquency among Unsupervised Adolescents" serves as a

direct legal basis for the implementation of the prosecutor's oversight activity in the field of legal education in general, specialized, and professional educational institutions.

According to Article 2 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prosecutor's Office," one of the main tasks of the prosecutor's offices is to prevent and combat legal violations. Similarly, the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan is considered the coordinating body of the Republican Interdepartmental Commission on the Prevention of Offenses and Combating Crime.

In this regard, in order to prevent and combat the neglect and delinquency of minors in the republic, relevant collaborative measures such as "Usmir," "Davomat," "O'quvchi," "G'amxorlik," and "Oyna" are regularly organized in cooperation with appropriate organizations. Specifically, according to S.M. Astanov, the analysis of offenses committed by juveniles indicates that in 20% of cases, the time of the offense corresponds to the time when minors should be attending classes, while in 80% of cases, this indicator corresponds to their free time from studies.

The results of the analytical data compiled by the Prosecutor General's Office indicate that during the months of January to August 2023, more than 6,000 targeted measures were taken directly by the enforcement of laws related to minors, especially aimed at raising awareness among the wider community, particularly the youth, to prevent neglect and delinquency. Additionally, over 2,000 releases were made through various mass media outlets.

We can easily state that measures such as these implemented by the prosecutor's offices effectively prevent the occurrence of legal violations among minors. In this regard, the assertion made by S. Khojaqulov that "delinquency does not occur on its own, but rather results from the failure to address the causes and conditions that allow it to occur in a timely manner" resonates with our perspective.

Indeed, the importance of implementing preventive measures is emphasized not only by modern experts but also by the Dutch philosopher Desiderius Erasmus[9].

Similarly, the aforementioned legal documents indicate the oversight of the prosecutor's office over the adherence to laws in general, specialized, and professional educational institutions. For instance, Article 9 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Youth Policy" highlights the participation of prosecuting authorities and institutions in implementing the youth policy.

In addition, the prosecutor's office oversees the precise and uniform implementation of the legal documents on the youth policy, actively participates in the legislative activities regarding the youth policy field, and enforces the prevention of legal violations among the youth. This includes identifying the reasons for the occurrence of legal violations, eliminating contributing factors, and promoting the legal rights and legal consciousness of young people.

Likewise, the legal basis of the prosecutor's oversight over the implementation of laws concerning unattended minors includes important documents such as decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Cabinet of Ministers. According to B. Saifulloyev, "In our country, the legal mechanism for assisting children and youth in their spiritual, intellectual, physical, and moral development is established based on more than 40 legal documents and decrees concerning the activities of children and youth."

The advancement of societal needs is contributing to the continuous improvement of our country's legal system. Especially, the establishment of new institutions to protect the rights of unattended minors is underway. In particular, the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 9, 2021, No. PF-6275, on "Additional Measures to Improve the System of Safeguarding the Rights and Guarantees of Unattended Minors" plays a significant role in enhancing the legal foundations for the protection of the rights and guarantees of unattended minors, as well as the prevention of neglect and legal violations among them. Based on this Decree, the Institute of the Oliy Majlis for the Protection of Children's Rights was established, as well as national and regional commissions on children's issues, including the National Commission for Children's Affairs at the Republican

Interdepartmental Commission, the Karakalpakstan Republic, regions, and the city of Tashkent, as well as district (city) interdepartmental commissions for children's issues.

Notably, the Head of the General Prosecutor's Office and relevant regional prosecutors were included in the structure of national and regional commissions on children's issues. These reforms underscore the importance of protecting the rights of unattended minors as a crucial aspect of our country's social life, emphasizing the need to adhere to and enforce separate legal procedures and oversight.

Indeed, it is essential to emphasize the creation of a new organizational and legal mechanism for establishing the supervision of unattended individuals' rights and protecting their legal benefits. In particular, some legal scholars argue that the lack of legal definition of the subject of supervision in the field of unattended individuals undermines the effectiveness of organizing the activities of the prosecutor's office. Additionally, A.S. Arutyunyan underscores that ensuring independent monitoring of the enforcement of laws on unattended individuals contributes significantly to the effective implementation of the laws governing unattended individuals[10]. In this matter, we fully respect the opinions of these authors.

In our opinion, according to Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prosecutor's Office," it is essential for the prosecutor's oversight on the enforcement of legislation regarding individuals who do not have access to legal assistance to be included. Simultaneously, as an integral part of ensuring the quality of law enforcement in the field of non-enforcement, the inclusion of prosecutor oversight on the enforcement of legislation in general, special, and professional educational institutions is essential. This is because if we aim to improve the quality of attention and education provided to the younger generation today, it is necessary to simultaneously organize supervisory measures.

The implementation of these changes contributes to the effectiveness of the oversight of the prosecutor's office in general, special, and professional educational institutions, further strengthening the legal foundation in this area. Moreover, it emphasizes the importance of protecting the rights of individuals who do not have

access to legal assistance as one of the crucial and essential tasks of the prosecutor's office.

In Resolution No. 139 of the General Prosecutor of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2017, concerning the enhancement of the effectiveness of the prosecutor's oversight in the field of individuals who do not have access to legal assistance, a set of requirements was specified. Specifically, ensuring the strengthening of legality, ensuring the integrity of the law, protecting the rights, freedoms, and legal interests of individuals who do not have access to legal assistance, preventing negligence, misconduct, illegal activities, and crime among individuals who do not have access to legal assistance, identifying enabling conditions and terms, and preventing them were defined as the primary tasks of the prosecutor's office, aiming to enhance the form and methods of supervision based on the enforcement of legislation regarding individuals who do not have access to legal assistance.

Likewise, in the implementation of this supervision, the responsibilities for ensuring the health, social protection, education, and spiritual and physical development of minors and children deprived of parental care, the prevention of neglect and delinquency among individuals who do not have access to legal assistance, and monitoring, inspecting, and prosecuting all pre-trial actions in compliance with the law are specified. These tasks require the prosecutors' staff to be fully responsible for carrying out supervision in this area. According to A. Davletov's opinion, "The responsibilities of prosecutors in the enforcement of legislation regarding individuals who do not have access to legal assistance are extensive, and they are closely related to the supervision areas or their direction".

In light of the added point, it is essential to delineate the monitoring measures related to enhancing the quality of education in the field and to underscore its distinct significance.

In conclusion, legal principles serve as the key foundations governing various aspects of societal life, particularly the basics of managing the education sector. General, specialized, and vocational education institutions play a crucial role in

ensuring oversight from prosecutors regarding the implementation of these legal foundations. Specifically:

Firstly, establishing a solid foundation for organizing the oversight of educational institutions is critical. They outline the laws and regulations that educational institutions must adhere to. Prosecutors can ensure the implementation of the designated guidelines within the activities of educational institutions, understanding these legal principles. These institutions' activities promote justice, fairness, and accountability.

Secondly, educational institutions need to comply with various legal requirements, including ensuring student safety, adhering to curriculum standards, and financial accountability. Legal foundations provide prosecutors with the opportunity to conduct thorough examinations and evaluations in accordance with legal documents.

Thirdly, prosecutors contribute to the enforcement of oversight based on legal principles, ensuring compliance with the legal framework in the field of education. This helps to maintain the legal framework of educational institutions and prevents undue influence or corruption.

Fourthly, the legal framework lays the groundwork for the continuous improvement of the activities of educational institutions. Regular review and updating of laws and regulatory documents facilitate the adaptability of the legal framework to the evolving needs of the education sector.

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